

Appendix B

Meeting Transcript

After the conclusions and bibliographical references, the text used to complete the dissertation is presented in this numbered annex.

B.1 Audio Transcript 2

SPEAKER 1: Okay, sorry for my English. I'm not using English for, I don't know, two or three years, so it's difficult for me to speak properly. But I think we can manage here. I'm sure you are used to a lot of people speaking English so you understand me. So how is your Portuguese? Inexistent.

SPEAKER 2: Mais ou menos.

SPEAKER 1: Ok, so we are KOVASU. In reality we have another name here in Portugal. We are trying to change the name because we have also a company in Angola which is called Cobazo. So the idea, we made the company here in Portugal in one hour, so for us it was not possible to choose the name. They provide us a list of possible names and we choose the most idiotic name for our company from the list of 50. So now we are in the process of changing it. So we are very new. Tomorrow we will sign our first deal, our first contract. We are working with a foundation, a Spanish foundation that is developing activities in Angola within a European Union project. So we are starting now in reality. We have several other activities, especially in the Portuguese company, but our aim is also to involve the Angolan company in these activities. So we are very busy right now. But the idea of KOVASU is to work globally and when I heard that you were from Lagos I was very amused because that's the kind of person that we need to work with us because you have the vision you know you know the context where we work and I'm assuming that you lived in Nigeria and you maybe you are European I don't know. You are Nigerian so you saw the cars from the NGOs cruising in the capital I'm sure, United Nations so that's our world, that's how we work. So you know what we do in reality.

So these organizations, they have a lot of projects with a lot of money. And sometimes they have lots of difficulties in dealing with this managing of certain process in the project cycle for instance financing the finance sector in the future we will address this issue specifically but now we are talking about monitoring and evaluation when attorney and evaluation in reality is a very simple thing.

Normally there is a tool, which is the logical framework, that sends some examples, at least two. But there are several models.

It's a pity Joao is not here because I asked him to share other types of logical frameworks and I asked him to come but he's not feeling well, so he's in Coimbra. He's not feeling well so he's not been able to join us and to participate in this early stages of our project. project and yeah you must at least get this it is very important that he receives these different possibilities these different models models because there are plenty of them the question is you only use one type of model? No. Or it depends on the client? Yes, it depends on the client. And the idea is to have one of the main activities is to construct the logical framework. To help teams, to help the people that are starting the project, building the logical framework, which is a military tool from the Second World War.

Americans invented the logical framework when they went to war and they defined objectives, blah, blah, blah, general, specific activities, everything you see there.

So the developing world, the developing business, let's say it, took this tool and uses it since the 50s or since the 60s from the last century.

So one of the things that this system could help people is to build the logical framework. For that we need to put in the system four or five different models and another one which is completely open and people can define which variables they want in the logical framework.

SPEAKER 3: Do you understand, Michael? Speaker 2 I will catch up.

SPEAKER 1: Just... If you don't understand, you interrupt me. Because my English is like what you hear, it's terrible. Just give me 10 minutes and it will improve. So, let's see.

SPEAKER 2: You are saying that. . .

SPEAKER 1: You have 3, 4, 5 five it doesn't have yeah four or five and one open okay the ideal would be that you can always load a new one yeah you can load anyone of course but I place I sent you two and they are from the European Union because we are working with you I think you know what you I think I think the interesting I think what we could do would be try to have predefined ones yes with names I want this one. Pluck! It's done. Or I want... UNDP, FAO, United Nations, whatever... ..already there. And one where they say, no, I want one defined by me. I want this from UNDP, I want this from the United Nations... Build your own. from UNDP, I want this from the United Nations, sorry, a review.

SPEAKER 2: Build your own.

SPEAKER 1: And I want to put something by mine that is nowhere. Speaker [Professor Marian] Build my own. What's B-M-O?

SPEAKER 1: Build my own. Okay?

SPEAKER 2: No, it's more like the custom model.

SPEAKER 3: So we have the predefined models and we have the custom model.

SPEAKER 1: And then we have the custom model.

SPEAKER 3: Where you can, I'm not sure if this is possible, but you are building something and the system is proposing alternatives

SPEAKER 1: or proposing the next steps. If you have general objectives, let's put here some specific objectives.

SPEAKER 3: That's difficult.

SPEAKER 1: In the future.

SPEAKER 3: No, no, no. I'm not saying it's impossible, but then you have to, on the background of this, you need to have some metadata where you catalog each type of variable. And then you see, oh, I only have variables of general objectives. You should have one of the main objectives. So you have to have metadata to it. You understand what I'm saying?

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: So here, when you talk about a logical framework, you talk about columns, right?

SPEAKER 1: Sorry, Mariana.

SPEAKER 3: So, columns, right? And each column has a name, correct? Yes, and there are also columns, right? And each column has a name, correct? Yes, and there are also horizontal variables. Oh, and then you have horizontal variables. It's a matrix.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, it's a matrix.

SPEAKER 1: But the user will be seeing it as a file.

SPEAKER 3: Do you want to print one, just to see how it is? I sent you this.

SPEAKER 2: No, I have one.

SPEAKER 1: This one. sent you this this one yeah yes yes it's totally important that's not important look Look, result chain indicator, reference base, target, actual, value, this is, well, these are Spanish people writing in Portuguese, so this is verification sources of Fontes de Dados. And this is... How is Presupostos in English?

SPEAKER 2: I don't know. Presupostos is...

SPEAKER 1: This will happen, but if there is a civil war, forget it.

SPEAKER 3: It's a presupposto. It's a precondition.

SPEAKER 1: You understand? I'm good. So this is normal. This precondition. You understand? So this is normal. This precondition is normal. But there are logical frameworks in English on the internet. But is it possible to print this way? And then, look, we have horizontal ones. So this is the... Can you read it? Because I'm blind almost. General objective. the general objective, improve the quality of life of young people

and women, including ethnic minorities in the provinces of Tata, Tatatata and Angola. Assumptions. Assumptions. The presupposto is the assumption. We will improve the quality of life of young people and women if, that is an assumption, if there is women or if there is young people, if there is no civil war. They didn't put anything there because they are not very competent people in Madrid. Not big at all. sorry so and then look here here this is one specific objective so this is the general objective and this is the specific objective and the specific objective is opportunities of employment for young people in the proof is in the provinces of Luanda we learn Conan are Qunan are improved. So we need, generally we want to improve the life of young people and women. And how we do it? Specifically getting more opportunities of employment for young people. They forgot women here, maybe there is another specific objective fields with with text or numbers right so it says the the base reference base value and year of reference so 14.62, it's a decimal, and then the year.

SPEAKER 3: So you need to, I think, create here a database model with all these variables.

But if it's custom module, you have to ask, what is the name and what is the type of the variable right if it's a number if it's a string

SPEAKER 2: just because I've worked on a project that looks like this, it is used in a company to actually track KPIs, employee performance right from when they are onboarded in an organization, not just projects like this. And this is the way it works.

SPEAKER 1: KPI. What's a KPI?

SPEAKER 2: Like performance measure, performance indicators. To know...

SPEAKER 1: Are they indicators?

SPEAKER 2: We have indicators here.

SPEAKER 3: Let him finish.

SPEAKER 2: Now, this is the way it works. So we have different models. We have a generic model that captures it's more like a higher model where other models actually fit in. So it contains every data that you can ever think of. So with that we now have when the user comes to the platform and probably let's say they want to create for an organization they want to create a project so they will see a custom template a predefined custom template that shows probably things that people have used before so they could just click on that and it populates everything for them so they will see the name maybe organization A organization B so just just the word just a name so they can select that it has the objectives it has the colors it has where to put the organization logo it has the kpis and everything. when you do not have a custom template where you select a custom template from the admin model i mean admin part okay the admin we create how the form is going to look like take for instance maybe number of KPIs and other information

SPEAKER 3: Show the indicators, he also has indicators

SPEAKER 2: I think there is this existing system I can show you. We have indicators and we have the targets.

SPEAKER 1: Right now it's 10 but we want to achieve 80. That's our target and continuously we want to know the performance of the project. For instance today we are in 20 next week we are in 30 you understand and this information will feed a dashboard yeah and the dashboard is for people who doesn't want they don't want to know anything about this kind of tools they just want to look they are financing the project or they are the beneficiaries to go as they and they want to know how is the performance of the project in Delta T in that moment my question is it's not here in this those indicators are here

SPEAKER 3: yes there I'm going to bring the paper. Ah, okay.

SPEAKER 2: I think there is a particular tool during my research that actually did something like that. I think having a visual look will help, maybe if we are actually on the same page. So I'm trying to get that particular website. I put it in the state of art analysis I think it's really Yeah, the result.

SPEAKER 1: Thank you. so Ron is not feeling good here, look.

SPEAKER 2: That's the problem.

SPEAKER 1: He's fine now. Feeling better. He's with depression.

SPEAKER 2: Depression.

SPEAKER 1: You know depression?

SPEAKER 2: Yes.

SPEAKER 1: Sometimes it's not easy. He has good days and bad days.

SPEAKER 2: Stress.

SPEAKER 1: It's frustrating. See, sometimes it's not easy because he has good days and bad days. It's frustrating. Yeah, it's frustrating, right? All right. Thank you. so This is a tool, sorry, it's a similar tool.

SPEAKER 2: Oh, Tola Data.

SPEAKER 1: Tola Data.

SPEAKER 2: Yeah. So I checked it and I think it's almost the same thing with what you want to do. And it's just the same way you create a project from the admin side you specify the way you want the form to actually look like how you want to collect the data and I think they also have predefined models

SPEAKER 1: okay yes I never seen but I heard talking about this yeah we have to all our data

SPEAKER 2: we have dev results we have web more before I've used the H is I've used it before the the app itself

SPEAKER 3: okay so we need to do something similar to this but we need to do it differently. Something must be different.

SPEAKER 2: So in the state of the art, I captured based on what I've been able to see here, I put them there and what we can actually do differently. And also some other existing tools.

SPEAKER 1: I'm going to see it closely and understand how it functions.

SPEAKER 3: I am sorry but it is not working.

SPEAKER 2: We were talking about similar systems, tools that already exist.

SPEAKER 3: Now, the secret here is to add something.

SPEAKER 1: I hear a lot about this Tola Data, I have never used it, but I hear a lot about this pen, I never used it but I hear a lot about this pen. Have you printed it? them because it's not working maybe I don't have a folder but I'm going to print Speaker [Professor Diana] so you already understood the dynamics of this or I think I understand this a bit with the way it has been explained.

SPEAKER 2: Having a predefined model, let's see if we can, I think it's calling it model but what the user is seeing is just more like a board, a tab where they can just click and select this custom but from the database it's already configured they just select it and just auto-populate whatever they need, just create the project entirely and auto-populate it.

SPEAKER 3: I think he understood so now that's one of the requirements to you already have I think you could go and go through what you have already put in your document.

SPEAKER 2: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: And go through and see with Miguel if there is something missing there. I'll come with the document, okay?

SPEAKER 1: I'm sorry.

SPEAKER 2: Open the Google Docs.

SPEAKER 1: Okay. I'm sorry .

SPEAKER 2: okay you still don't you have access to the document I'm sorry do you have access to

SPEAKER 1: this no I could not access to it

SPEAKER 2: so let me reshare it again oh you this is your email

SPEAKER 1: yes but when i open when i try to open it with my email from from the from field appears i i don't understand what's going on let me send another email. You see this is one possibility project description indicators source of verification assumptions verification assumptions clean the water, overall objective, general objective specific objective, results you can end results you can have outputs and outcomes but the end, activities the things that we have to do in order to and then in the indicators you you can you can have the target measures the extent of issue contribution to the overall benefit so you can subdivide this in several columns sources of verification is where you go to find the information that assures that you have achieved that objective or achieve this output you understand and here you have to upload documents for instance photographs reports signing terms whatever so we need to have space for people to upload documents assumptions is factors outside the project that you don't control sometimes you cannot you cannot achieve this specific objective because of these factors that you cannot control there is always factors that you cannot control so

this is one possibility but there are others so I think this is this could be interesting so this is the base tool in order to organize result monitoring system

SPEAKER 2: yeah So, if I get you right, it means before you actually even create a project, or anyone creates a project, this needs to be specified.

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 2: The baseline, the KPIs, that is what you're going to use to track...

SPEAKER 1: And it's not one person, it's a collective task. So you understand that's not you alone creating this it has no value it's sometimes these projects are developed in cooperation with several entities and they go together they they have to participate in this discussion so it means we have a zoom you have three users you can have three users yes user b and user c yes user a actually creates the kpis the templates and probably sent to user b and user c or it's available there and user b is going to get in and say i don't agree with this

SPEAKER 3: maybe we should put this the indicator is too low

SPEAKER 1: we have to put a higher indicator you understand so it's a negotiation process

SPEAKER 3: so you have different organizations you can have different organizations this one have you printed not yet there are I are three or four. One in university, one in an employment center.

SPEAKER 2: It's a project with different users.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, from different organizations or several users inside only one organization.

SPEAKER 3: So there is a kind of hierarchical... Right? The same with 2D2.

SPEAKER 1: It's the same of 2D2.

SPEAKER 3: So you have a project where you have users from 01 user or 02 and this can have different logins maybe 01 or 02 it's a user as organization so this is not a login the login is here correct but this login is from this and my question is do the organizations have different privileges

SPEAKER 1: normally there's a coordinator this is one it's one who is living it's the organization or a specific you the organization and inside each organization there's a leader so a coordinator so you have this right and then you have one it's a different one all the same as the super no one is the supervisor there

SPEAKER 3: are other people participating in the process yes yes And then you have the... no other, all the others are the same.

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: Yes? So now we have to say the Bloom, what are the tasks we can do in the system?

SPEAKER 1: Yes, I think they can participate in everything, but then is a hard supervisor as to...

SPEAKER 3: This admin creates to validate to validate their their work

SPEAKER 1: you you can use colors to distinguish all this design me creates users inside of one but not inside of course but this one cannot create users yes this super it's very when you create a project you have to say which is the organism what which are the organizations we have to say which one is the admins to the board.

In Fresa, which is European Union, there was four co-managers. So are the greens. And I was the admin of this one. I was this person here. And I had a team of 5 or 6 people working together. And then I had, look, this is crazy, 19 projects. So that was, it was a mess. No, okay. It was another level.

SPEAKER 3: So you have a project A and you is the project B? We are talking about two themes.

SPEAKER 2: So you are saying that you told this is a project with a logical framework? Speaker Look, this in reality...

SPEAKER 1: It's always like that. We think we are understanding, they come out and... So, let's call this program. Program and project.

SPEAKER 2: Program.

SPEAKER 3: I'm going to bring the things.

SPEAKER 1: And project. Okay.

SPEAKER 2: Project, like she said, project one, project two, project three and project four.

SPEAKER 1: We did the same program. We did the same program. We did the same program. But this was very complex.

SPEAKER 2: What is a program?

SPEAKER 3: Now that is where he is mixing it up.

SPEAKER 2: Because according to our data, this is our networks where you come to our platform as a super admin. So you are...

SPEAKER 3: That's something else. So now you are something else that is looking out so now the inside the platform inside of programs so let's say we have a project the first project

SPEAKER 2: no no you can't see program okay we... Let's start this one. And this is for the future. Because this was... I'm going... Look, look, look.

SPEAKER 1: Wait, wait, wait. It's a simple project. A simple project from one organization. Or a project with three organizations. A simple thing. like this one.

SPEAKER 2: Okay.

SPEAKER 2: We have a program, call it project.

SPEAKER 1: Project.

SPEAKER 2: And the project has three partners.

SPEAKER 1: Three partner organizations are developing this project, okay?

SPEAKER 2: Okay, so we have... Partner A, B and C. I don't have black, but I have more if the beam goes out.

SPEAKER 1: Partner A.

SPEAKER 2: Right.

SPEAKER 1: We have B.

SPEAKER 2: Partner B and partner C. they are working on this project.

SPEAKER 3: 3:36 You want another pen?

SPEAKER 1: This is it.

SPEAKER 2: Thank you.

SPEAKER 1: They are working on project E

SPEAKER 2: yes project X project S what is so the What is? So, the partner A is the super admin, you told?

SPEAKER 1: Okay, this is...

SPEAKER 2: In each one is an admin.

SPEAKER 1: Super admin? There is always an administrator, BA and CA.

SPEAKER 2: But this is also a super admin because this organization is the leading one in this project.

SPEAKER 1: Do you understand?

SPEAKER 2: So they could have more little administrations.

SPEAKER 1: What can I say?

SPEAKER 3: B, A, what is B?

SPEAKER 2: B is partner B.

SPEAKER 2: A is administrator.

SPEAKER 1: Okay, so this is administration of the partner C, administration of partner B. And then you can have little administration, technicians that work, but the validation is always done from these ones and at the end it is this one who validates everything okay i'm not sure if i'm viewing

SPEAKER 2: so now i guess the parts that we have different partners and partner is uh the lead probably

SPEAKER 1: they are the sole owner of of the projects we can use it that way. So because of that, that's the owner of the project.

SPEAKER 2: So we make them the super admin. And it can be working alone or in partnership with other partners. So we have to condition is either they are working on this project alone or they invite other partners.

SPEAKER 1: Exactly. And they will be the one to give the privilege they want different partners. Now, where are these? Now the second step is KPIs,

SPEAKER 2: this line and the rest. So when they are creating, when partner A is creating the project, partner A will create the, using the model, the baseline.

SPEAKER 3: Baseline. The baseline. So you talked about sending it to different other partners to validate to check baseline is an it's an exercise I will not use that that work okay okay so but look you have indicators indicators and and you have this there's look there is an general objective overall objective

SPEAKER 1: sorry sorry sorry I'm not sure if this could be in the same the same context

SPEAKER 3: context but you have overall objective specific objectives and then you have results and you have activities

SPEAKER 1: okay and let's put different colors here this is this is right okay Ok? And can you put it in green?

SPEAKER 3: And you can have specific objective 1, 2, 3. And this can have different colors because of the effect.

SPEAKER 1: It is possible for the specific objective.

SPEAKER 3: 3 is this partner, partner C. The gold is here, I'm going to open the window.

SPEAKER 2: It's not here, it's just here.

SPEAKER 1: We are used to it.

SPEAKER 3: You understand? okay okay you understand yeah and activities the same thing activity one

SPEAKER 1: could be activity two but activity three is partner B so it's me it's me sorry or different the department this partner can create different activities for the sole partners.

SPEAKER 3: Yes.

SPEAKER 1: And we can have a, well, it could be complicated.

SPEAKER 2: Tricky?

SPEAKER 1: Tricky, same.

SPEAKER 2: I think it starts with first understanding this so that we can create a model that actually matches.

SPEAKER 3: starts with face understanding is so that we can create in modern and actually much and what do you say okay

SPEAKER 1: you have indicators metatarget metatarget you need to have what hate you it's the target and we are at 20 now so you have to work it's a time it's a target but it's a number it could be a number yeah so the indicator here is for

SPEAKER 3: instance number of employments number of employments number of jobs or number of jobs created

SPEAKER 1: 100, that's the target

SPEAKER 2: What about the timeline? Yes, we have three years to complete the project.

SPEAKER 1: Here in 2025, 2026, 2027 The project finishes here. You could have months or so, but I'm putting it simple.

SPEAKER 3: So here is, in it's kind of milestones of

SPEAKER 1: the indicators and the 25 25 is the departure value in this case it's not. It could be zero. Sorry.

SPEAKER 3: There are other indicators that this does not start in zero.

SPEAKER 1: You understand?

SPEAKER 3: You start in the certain level.

SPEAKER 1: But in this case. The baseline.

SPEAKER 3: Yes.

SPEAKER 1: In this case it's zero because you want to create jobs.

SPEAKER 3: So it's zero.

SPEAKER 1: But you have value

SPEAKER 3: you know you are 30

SPEAKER 1: You have to define the end value that you want to achieve.

SPEAKER 3: And then you have to define the values, the milestones values.

SPEAKER 1: For instance, I'm going to say a very stupid thing. Number of children per women.

SPEAKER 2: Okay.

SPEAKER 3: No? No, we already understood, Miguel. Twelve. No, we are not going to use that that example please okay no I don't think it's a good example okay it's not a target no number of households with toilets inside. Okay.

SPEAKER 2: What's it?

SPEAKER 1: So we have 20So this is a percentage which is very complicated then but imagine that we here we are at 40

SPEAKER 3: And the idea is... That is for the project, that those indicators with targets are for each project.

SPEAKER 1: No.

SPEAKER 2: It's for this guy here, which is the super administrator.

SPEAKER 1: Thank you. later thank you this guy here we will define who has access to the information. first this could be very interesting for the organizations that are financing the project and they don't want to know only during the three years of the project in three moments what's going on they want to know each month for instance so it's 3 plus 12 and they we can have look we can have a graphic like this you see if we have artificial intelligence and I know Those are already analysis. And if we have artificial intelligence, we can translate this in text. Like Kobo Kobo. [Speaker 3] You are going too far. We need to do more simple things to start and then we will see.

SPEAKER 1: Ok, so one thing is, there are three steps here. The first one is to build the logical framework.cThe second one is to feed the logical framework. Periodically, continuously, you have to define the system for instance in this last project we feed it three in three months we feed it it's terrible but you can feed it constantly each time you create a latrine or you you have a training session with women and young people, you feed the logical framework.

SPEAKER 2: So you come to the platform and fill in the details, right?

SPEAKER 1: Yes. So you can fill it on a permanent basis or each month or each year, you understand? It's for this guy here to define in which periodicity he is going to feed. Another input data on the system. It's a lot of information that he is giving like... I'm sorry, but you have...

SPEAKER 2: Yeah, and before that stipulated time, all the other partners, the co-partners receive a notification reminding them to come to the platform. Yes, they don't know, they

SPEAKER 1: they don't need to receive that information because they are following what's happening the logical framework. So you have two two steps one is to build a logical framework. Step number two is to feed the logical framework. Step number three is to translate what is what's going to feed the logical framework. Step number three is to translate what is going on in the logical framework in a dashboard for normal people, not for specialists. With logos that you can choose from people eating, people reading...

SPEAKER 3: Yeah, but you need to say what information you want on the dashboard of course but we'll go back to that later I'm a bit worried with it I want you to listen to that three different good steps okay okay so when I left you were discussing program project the users okay you already understood

SPEAKER 2: yeah what we have here is but not a is it one of the projects so automatically is a super army right you can choose to work on this alone or he has others and these other co-partners working on this project should have different roles like the admin, right?

SPEAKER 1: That is okay, it was what we defined, right? And so there's one admin and then simple users for each partner. So the platform will have... but then Miguel came with the thing that, oh but then I have many projects, he said. Remember?

SPEAKER 2: Yeah, a partner can have different projects and for each different project can assign based on who or what. Of course. So a partner can be a super admin in a project and can be a normal partner in another project.

SPEAKER 1: Exactly.

SPEAKER 2: It means partner B in another project can be the owner, while partner A is a normal admin.

SPEAKER 3: But look, plan, program, project, activity. So we are on the level of project, right?

SPEAKER 1: Plan.

SPEAKER 2: And then activity, which is the feeding of the logical framework, I suppose.

SPEAKER 1: We are going only to work from here down.

SPEAKER 2: So why? Why can't we you introduce this entropy? Now we are going to work on it. In the future we will see.

SPEAKER 1: Because a program is...

SPEAKER 1: It can have several projects. A program can have several projects and each project several activities. They are talking about different levels. For instance, Freza, where I was working, it was a program and it had four projects. And I was working at the program level with the European Union as a monitor and then I finished my contract and I started with Camois, which was a project. But this was a program. I think we can put that level there.

SPEAKER 2: So like the ones that control.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, it's finance. Sometimes there's no program. Sometimes it's an isolated project. So you create a user which is not of this type, project owners and project partners, but it's a... we need to give another name to that.

SPEAKER 3: Finance...

SPEAKER 1: Promoter.

SPEAKER 3: Promoter.

SPEAKER 1: And the promoter has access to several... At the level of our discussion I propose that we work from project below.

SPEAKER 2: I'm just thinking if we don't start from program it should be very difficult to scale back to starting from here if we don't define this from the beginning.

SPEAKER 3: I agree with you. So that's why I'm... He says, no, but then, what he's saying is, I'm going to translate. What he's saying is that if we start with a project, then it can be difficult to get back to the top. So I think we should create this plan, program, project, think about what you want from these people who finance you.

SPEAKER 2: What is the difference then? What is the plan?

SPEAKER 1: The plan is political.

SPEAKER 3: Okay, no plan. Delete plan.

SPEAKER 1: So, Fresa, Fortalecime, it's an example. Fresa, for... I was... Fresa is European Union, okay? I was working with them, with European Union, monitoring the old projects, one, two, three, four. And then, finished my contract and I passed to Camois. Camois is the Portuguese Cooperation Services. So this was 68 million euros. Which means that this was the biggest project within this program, Fresa. This was FAO, United Nations, UNDP, and Spanish research hospital whatever this was a this was not development this was a study those are the ones that give the money 45 45 and the rest of the money was what okay so you can have several...

SPEAKER 3: This is the program, this is the program. And the different users can find a...

SPEAKER 1: This is the project.

SPEAKER 3: But...

SPEAKER 2: No, this is the project.

SPEAKER 1: Yeah, this is the project.

SPEAKER 2: This is the program, and for the program there are different projects.

SPEAKER 1: Okay? For the program there are different projects. But, in the case of Camões, it was my nightmare. They had Implementação Direta, Direct Implementation, and what... I have to pee. It's the same here. Subventions. So, there were 19...

SPEAKER 2: You have to pee, sorry.

SPEAKER 3: He needs to go to the toilet.

SPEAKER 2: You have to pee.

SPEAKER 2: It's the same here, Miguel. You go out, turn left...

SPEAKER 1: We don't call it projects, we call it subventions. Because we give money to the NGOs to develop activities. And they have their own logical framework. And that logical framework fed the main...

SPEAKER 2: Oh, I get it. ...framework.

SPEAKER 1: And there was a confusion because... Still on the same platform. confusion because still on the same platform sorry still on the same platform the same software yeah no I'm just saying that they are very complicated but yeah look yeah when you vote she's worried no I'm not going to pee in my trousers

SPEAKER 2: I think you should go to the bathroom and come back.

SPEAKER 3: Miguel, go to the bathroom. We continue. Where is the bathroom? If you use the restroom then you're on with them continuing.

SPEAKER 1: I lost my glasses, My eyeglasses.

SPEAKER 2: This is it.

SPEAKER 3: go Miguel. That's the paper you're using. Take a picture of that.

SPEAKER 1: Okay.

SPEAKER 3: I know what the O, O, S, O, R and A are.

SPEAKER 1: No, no, different projects.

SPEAKER 2: So the subvention is more like a project? It's a project, it's a micro project. It can have a custom model or a different model. Yeah, but it's not normal.

SPEAKER 3: So how do you end up here?

SPEAKER 1: I mean, it's a chaos. So I think it was a very big challenge.

SPEAKER 3: I should say same logical framework so that you can sum up and then you have...

SPEAKER 1: What are you talking about? The same model or...

SPEAKER 3: Logical frame.

SPEAKER 1: The same content or model?

SPEAKER 2: The model and content is a bit tricky now to me.

SPEAKER 3: I don't know if it's a model or content. We are talking about logical frameworks.

SPEAKER 1: Yeah, but the activities, the objectives, they are all different from the 19... And from this 4 and from the 19.

SPEAKER 3: I'm talking about the logical framework. Of course, a micro project has different goals and activities.

SPEAKER 1: Okay, there's always the same... Logical framework. And the logical framework of the European Union. Okay, if it's the European Union. It's the same. So that's it. The problem is that...

SPEAKER 3: That helps. They hire... Micro projects have the same logical framework.

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: Of course, each project will have different activities and...

SPEAKER 2: Yeah, they will have different activities. But I think the objective should be cascaded down to the sub-projects, right? So they have the same goal, but different activities and different... Probably ways of doing things.

SPEAKER 1: Yeah, the problem is that they hire a technical assistant to analyze the proposals they had. They had terms of reference and the NGOs, they proposed projects. And they hire a couple of Dutch people. And they analyze the... And they say that's everything okay. And the problem is that the logical frameworks of the subventions did not fit directly the above logical framework. For instance, here we need to make 40 schools, primary schools. And none of the subventions was promoting primary schools.

SPEAKER 2: So there was no match.

SPEAKER 1: There was no match. There was a big divorce. A 60s divorcee. A big... There was no match. There was no match. And it was... And I was in the position that I needed to analyze all that.

SPEAKER 3: Ah, that is interesting. So you come to the project and you say we need to have... Sorry. We need to have schools, 20 schools and 20 toilets.

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: And then this will have to come somewhere here. If you arrive here and you say we need 20 chairs, what do you say? But there's no goal on the above project that talks about chairs. That intelligentsia, I think we should do this. Do you understand, Miguel, what I'm saying?

SPEAKER 1: No, I was taking a picture. I'm sorry.

SPEAKER 3: So imagine that I say that I want 10 schools as numbers. 25 toilets.

SPEAKER 1: No, that's not a... No, school is an output. School is a result. Sorry. Okay.

SPEAKER 3: I want results. 10 schools, 25 toilets and two...

SPEAKER 1: Two restrooms.

SPEAKER 3: Restrooms. Okay. Those are the results I want from the project. But this project is made of three projects. Mine is a micro project. And here you say, okay. This thing has to have five... Five...

SPEAKER 1: Universities.

SPEAKER 3: Universities, right. And this one will have 10 tables.

SPEAKER 1: Shopping centers.

SPEAKER 3: Right. And five shopping centers. And this one will have 10 schools. I think that the software will say, okay. Okay. Not possible. This is not going to work. So I think you have to have kind of a framework where they have to choose which results will be on this. So you define this. And then when you go down and say, I have four micro projects to implement. And I say I want the 10 schools will be here. The 25 toilets will be here. You can, I don't know. Other things that were not there. But at least those have to be down here. So this is wrong. This one will say wrong. This is okay. But this one, it's not addressing the toilets and the restrooms.

SPEAKER 1: Yes. That's another thing. It's when you upload this information, you put 10 schools. You have the, one of the things is the sources of information. You need to prove that the schools were really built. So you need a document saying signed by the teacher, by the students or a photo.

SPEAKER 3: A photo.

SPEAKER 1: Yes. And when you have in the logical from 10 schools, you should click on this and go to the sources of verification.

SPEAKER 3: Prove that there's 10 schools.

SPEAKER 1: This guy can define which is acceptable. Photo, document of the government, whatever. Signatures, documents signed by the professors, whatever. So this is transparency. You understand?

SPEAKER 3: But you already moved to another topic.

SPEAKER 1: Yeah. Okay. I'm sorry.

SPEAKER 3: It's okay. My question really is, are we going to accept different results from the one that we are in the project? No.

SPEAKER 1: No, because it's not there that this is negotiated. It's before that. It's before that. When you define the logical framework of the subvention, if there is university, it's not acceptable because it doesn't fit the main logical framework. What is your overall objective? Objective in general. General objective.

SPEAKER 3: So you come to the project and you define.

SPEAKER 1: For example, improve the quality of education in Nigeria. It's an overall objective. Specific, creating schools. Results. Results. Improving the conditions of learning of young children and women. And how can we do? Building new schools in the model X. It's an output. And then there's the outcome.

SPEAKER 3: So?

SPEAKER 1: The outcome is not building schools. The output is the immediate result. We build a school.

But the outcome is what the students and the teachers do with that school. It's a long-term result. And there is also the impact.

SPEAKER 3: But do you want that there?

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: The problem is that. But you didn't put it there.

SPEAKER 1: No, because in Portuguese there's no difference between output and outcome. And that's a confusion. In all the Latin languages there is no. How so? The difference output. There are all results.

SPEAKER 3: When you define the project, you need to define the overall objective. You need to have specific objectives. It's one or several?

SPEAKER 2: Just one.

SPEAKER 1: One. You could have one or two, yes. One or two. They are not. You cannot have many. Specific objectives, there are more. It's equal or different. This one has only one. Here, there's only one. And as I understand, because I didn't read it, there's only one specific objective.

SPEAKER 3: Activity is M. One, two, three. These are Spanish people. It's a bit stupid. There are four and it's not possible. I would put M. It doesn't matter. So my question is, when you define the results, let's put ten schools, right?

SPEAKER 1: This is not a good example. This is not very well done.

SPEAKER 3: Twenty-five toilets and two dress rooms. Do you want to relate, Miguel? Just two. Do you want to relate the specific goals with the results?

SPEAKER 1: Yes. Yes. And activities. Each result has a...

SPEAKER 3: When you define an activity, you have to say that it's for this and for that.

SPEAKER 1: And the same for the objectives.

SPEAKER 3: This one is for this and this one is for this.

SPEAKER 1: I think this is a lot of information for him, but with time, you will...

SPEAKER 3: I can keep. And then, can you have one activity and have two different results?

SPEAKER 1: Yes. No. No? No.

SPEAKER 3: Can you have one result for many activities?

SPEAKER 1: One result? Yes.

SPEAKER 3: Can you have one SEO for many activities?

SPEAKER 1: One...

SPEAKER 3: One SEO?

SPEAKER 1: Many results, yes.

SPEAKER 3: And one results, okay? Two, many SEOs?

SPEAKER 1: Many... No. No. This is not possible.

SPEAKER 3: It's missing here. One overall objective to many SEOs? Yes.

SPEAKER 1: Of course.

SPEAKER 3: One overall to many, of course. Yes. And one SEO to many...

SPEAKER 1: Yes. Results.

SPEAKER 3: No. One overall to many...

SPEAKER 1: One overall to many... It's not read up, it's only read down.

SPEAKER 3: These, but you did the others.

SPEAKER 1: No, no, I don't know.

SPEAKER 3: One SEO to many... Yes. One SEO to many... It's only read down, okay.

SPEAKER 1: A general goal can have several specific goals, otherwise it doesn't make sense. It doesn't make sense to say it like this.

SPEAKER 3: So it doesn't make sense to say one R to one SEO? It doesn't make sense to say one R to one SEO? No. It's only read from top to bottom? Yes, from top to bottom. And not here either. One A to one R... Okay. It doesn't make sense to say it like this.

SPEAKER 1: From top to bottom.

SPEAKER 3: And also this urban program has... Projects. Projects. Okay. This one. I think we need another meeting. I think now we need to... Do you want to do mock-ups? Or...

SPEAKER 1: You are the expert here.

SPEAKER 3: In software engineering. Not me. Yeah, we haven't finished now. I think it's... You need to take a picture of this. Yeah. And... I don't know... Tomorrow I'm going abroad. And I'll come back the 25th.

SPEAKER 3: Indicators, how do you relate indicators? Indicators are related to the results.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, look what they have done here, in Spanish. They define the indicator. For instance, employment rate in the cities, disaggregated by sex, age and ethnic cultural group. And then there is the reference base. In 2024, the value was 32

SPEAKER 3: It's the starting point. Then they want to raise that.

SPEAKER 1: This is not very well done, because the target is lower than the...

SPEAKER 3: I want to sort out only this, because otherwise you are not going to do it. So, an activity has a number, has a description. What else? Then it relates to the results. Yes. Several results, R1, R2, for instance. What else? Is a person responsible for the activity? Miguel? Is a person responsible for the activity? Or participants in the activity? But participants are users of the system? No.

SPEAKER 1: Almost never.

SPEAKER 3: So, you don't put the names of the persons?

SPEAKER 1: No.

SPEAKER 3: And then these indicators that you put here, relate with the results. Yes? They are related with the results.

SPEAKER 1: The activities, yes.

SPEAKER 3: No. The indicators with the targets?

SPEAKER 1: You have indicators for all of them.

SPEAKER 3: Not for the activities. You have indicators for the overall objective?

SPEAKER 1: Yes.

SPEAKER 3: So, they have to be measurable?

SPEAKER 1: Yes. Normally, overall, it's the most difficult thing.

SPEAKER 3: And the specific objectives, and for the results.

SPEAKER 2: But we don't have the indicators now.

SPEAKER 1: Not for the activities. And then there's another thing, sometimes it's related to the activities, but I'm not seeing it here, which is the budget.

SPEAKER 3: Ah, ok. How do you define a project? O, O, S, O, R, then the activities. So, the budget of the activities, all summed up, goes to the budget of the project.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, but here we start to have a problem. Look, the specific objectives here are called results.

SPEAKER 3: Miguel.

SPEAKER 1: We start to have these problems that have to do with the language, you know?

I think this is important.

SPEAKER 3: But then, you discuss with your... Now, you're not going to...

SPEAKER 1: No, I have to discuss with him. But we are working in English, so...

SPEAKER 3: Yes, we don't have to discuss with him anything. Then you say, I want to put Portuguese, you are going to prepare the platform for multilingual. Ok? So, we start with Portuguese and English, and the possibility to add a new language. But it's a requirement, because you have other requirements than this. Yes? So, the project has a budget, but it's the sum up of all the...

SPEAKER 1: Sometimes, in each activity, there's a budget.

SPEAKER 3: And then you sum up all...

SPEAKER 1: That's not this case.

SPEAKER 3: Ok, but then you sum up all the budgets of the victim, and you have the global budget.

SPEAKER 1: Yes, or you have the budget of that result, because each result has a set of activities. You can say that result one, the budget is X, because you sum up all the budget of the activities of each result.

SPEAKER 3: Let's start with this, and then we bring the mock-ups, and we discuss over it. I think that we can put a name for the project, a description also for the project, and the different activities you... Ok? You define the results, and you are putting results here. Oh, and then you have the micro. So, when the project has micro, you have to start all over again. You have to define it. Right? If there's no micro, it's important, but you can have several micros. But the importance here is that you define what is one project, and then the possibilities of the other. The possibility of creating a big project with micro projects.

SPEAKER 2: Ok? Sure. So, it means a project will always have a budget.

SPEAKER 3: Sorry?

SPEAKER 2: A project? A project will have a budget.

SPEAKER 3: A budget.

SPEAKER 2: And each activity could have a budget.

SPEAKER 3: It's not obligatory.

SPEAKER 2: It's optional. Ok.

SPEAKER 3: And then he was saying things about budget and results, but we'll see that later. Ok?

SPEAKER 2: Ok.

SPEAKER 3: And then we'll have to see the dashboard. But first, we do this. Ok. I think we stop now. Stop.